

Efficient Content-based Image Retrieval Based on Anchor Point Selection in Manifold Ranking with Combined CNN and Low-Level Features

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(Received 19 September, 2023)

The paper describes the improvement of Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) system efficiency. In CBIR, where each image is typically represented by low-level features (description of color, texture, and shape). It is proposed to solve the following two limitations: (1) not only exploiting the basic similarity measure of images, the paper proposed to use an improved Efficient Manifold Ranking (EMR), where the improved Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) clustering algorithm is used to determine the anchor points of the EMR Graph and (2) EMR has not yet taken advantage of both low- and high-level features of the image, it is the second limitation. To solve this limitation, the cf-EMR method is chosen to combine low-level features and CNN, in which the image is ranked with improved EMR to get the outstanding advantages of both features types, thereby improving the quality of access. So that the accuracy of image retrieval systems to be improved. The average accuracy of more than 85% of the tests, performed on the three image datasets Logo2K+, VGGFACE2-S and Corel30K, indicates the high efficiency of our recommendations in improving the performance of the CBIR system.

AMS Subject Classification: 68W99

Keywords: bigdata, content-based image retrieval (CBIR), Efficient Manifold Ranking (EMR), Fuzzy C-Means (FCM), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10410163>

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1. Introduction

Over the years, CBIR has been noticed because of its usefulness in many real problems [1, 7, 16, 32]. In CBIR, a similarity measure is used to measure the distance between a query image and the images in the database [18]. The usual similarity measures, e.g. Euclidean and Minkowski type distances, which are applied in traditional image retrieval systems, reveal the inefficiency, especially with large real databases. Many research works [8, 33, 37] are focused on upgrading similarity measures in order to improve the performance of CBIR system that includes increasing calculation speed, reducing storage space and enhancing the accuracy of retrieval.

Typically, CBIR systems face some unexpected results due to two main reasons. The first cause is that authors often only explore basic similarity measures. This leads to the fact that sometimes the obtained results are not good as expected due to selecting inappropriate similarity measures or unclear thresholds (which easily causes false predictions), most evidently happened on real database [22, 26]. Even using the techniques, such as voting and relevance feedback (RF), does not significantly assist in improving the accuracy in these cases [8, 11]. Therefore, the similarity measures used in CBIR need to be improved or the thresholds are adjusted accordingly. The second reason, which also causes unexpected results in CBIR systems, is not taking advantage of both low-level and high-level features of images. Because the gap between these feature types is wide, research methods need to be optimized for the use of the beneficial characteristics of different features

[2, 17]. A dimensionality reduction method is also a solution for databases with manifold properties, however, the reduction only aims to improve computational efficiency on image features and does not focus on improving the retrieval accuracy in CBIR [11].

In recent years, to improve the accuracy of CBIR systems many studies have been carried out with the different similarity measures. Research on manifold ranking (MR) is a promising direction when MR is considered an effective similarity measure for searching similar images that is applied for not only image retrieval but also other problems. The original EMR emerged as one of the efficient similarity measures which is a variant of MR, widely used in CBIR, and gains outstanding results. Thanks to using and calculating only on the selected anchor points of images instead of looking across the entire database, this manifold ranking algorithm increases the computing speed of image retrieval, reduces the storage capacity of the database, and enhances the accuracy of manifold ranking. The clustering of large databases, which have manifold properties, is an important problem mentioned in recent years [33, 37]. However, most experiments have only succeeded with a small number of clusters or have slow processing speeds, such as in [9, 34]. Besides, the original EMR is considered as a method that uses successfully the traditional clustering algorithm as K-means for determining anchor points. Finding appropriate anchor points to build an EMR Graph is the prerequisite for improving the performance of CBIR systems by reducing processing time and the applicability of EMR to large databases. In this article, the main contributions are as follows:

- Concatenating low-level features (of texture, color and shape) and CNN features (extracted from a pre-trained model) into a combined one that contains the advantage characteristics of both these feature types.
- Proposing an algorithm $cf - EMR$ that can handle the lvdc condition for ranking

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images with their combined features.

- Accomplishing the experiments on three image datasets Logo2K+, VGGFACE2-S, and Corel30K (sorted in ascending order of visual complexity) and comparing the obtained results with other methods.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the work relating to the original and the improved EMRs. Section 2 presents our algorithm that is proposed for combining two feature types. A CBIR system description which is built up with cf-EMR is described in Section 3. Section 4 provides the experimental results, and the conclusion follows in Section 5.

2. The proposed combined algorithm

2.1. Theoretical background

Nowadays, there are many publications working on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) that relate to CBIR [6, 13]. The high-level characteristics of images could be obtained in the layers of pre-trained CNN or GCN networks, so the image retrieval quality is improved significantly. Krizhevsky et al. [15] succeeded in using the features extracted from the seventh layer of the Alexnet model in CBIR which is experimented on the ImageNet dataset. In [14], the authors proposed the TF-IDF features which are extracted from CNN to reinforce the image retrieval accuracy. In medical image processing, the authors in [24] proposed a new CNN model that is possible to learn the binary representations of images, thereby improving the retrieval quality of the medical image datasets of bone, joint, and lung. The results of these papers proved that the high-level features help CBIR systems enhance efficiency thanks to the property of their high discrimination. Besides the high-level features, the low-level features of images also play an important role in CBIR.

The experiments in [30] show that the advantage of low-level features is the invariance with the rotation and scale of images. In other words, when images are rotated or resized, their characteristics are still preserved and the image retrieval quality is not affected. However, there exists a significant drawback that low-level features depend greatly on the image quality and the lack of semantic information. In addition, low-level features do not follow Gaussian distribution, so the image processing (e.g. normalization) becomes more difficult and needs a more efficient solution as 3-sigma in [29]. In contrast, the convolutional neural network features (such as CNN or GCN), which are extracted from the early layers of pre-trained models, provide higher discrimination and are considered as a semantic representation of images. However, the limitation of high-level features is the reduction of color and texture details of images [6, 30]. The articles [13] mentioned these drawbacks of high-level features and also gave solutions for combining or mixing many features which even belong to different feature types. Due to the gap between low-level visual features and high-level semantic concepts being wide, calculating the similarity of images become ineffective and needs to be updated to match real problems [2, 17, 33]. Although the related experimental results indicate higher accuracy in CBIR, combining feature types of images is still a rational research direction to improve the quality of retrieval.

2.1.1. Efficient Manifold Ranking in CBIR

The accuracy of manifold ranking depends on the quality of anchor points and its performance is determined by the ability to handle the lvdc condition (short for a large number of image vectors, a large number of vector dimensions, and a large number of clusters). In this article, we propose using an improved algorithm EMR which is based on the actual observation that the experiments on several complex visual datasets with the original EMR

show the average accuracy is less than 80%. It is necessary to have a better clustering algorithm than K-means, which still can handle the lvdc condition and brings more efficiency for EMR with the target of higher average accuracy. We used FCM to replace K-means in determining the rational anchor points of an EMR Graph. Although the original FCM is considered to be more efficient than K-means in terms of accuracy, it requires more time to carry out several fuzzy calculations and iterations and is often applied to datasets with a small number of clusters and not high-dimensional vectors [4]. Our improved FCM (called *lvdc-FCM*) has overcome this limitation and admits the lvdc condition, thereby obtaining high retrieval accuracy, and can be applied to solve practical problems.

Unlike the standard manifold ranking algorithms in CBIR, the original algorithm EMR [37] focuses on selecting the number of anchors and then ranks the data points of an image database. The ranking of the images is based on the adjacent relations in an EMR graph that is represented

via these anchors and maintains a scalable graph construction. Because of this reason, EMR is applicable to rank efficiently on large databases and thereby enhancing the performance of CBIR systems.

An image feature vector E_i is called connected to E_j if $i \neq j$ and there exists a certain common anchor point A_c ($c = 1, 2, \dots, C$ and C is the number of anchors) such that A_c is the neighbor of both E_i and E_j . With each E_i notation, let us denote $N_b(i; s)$ that is a set of s anchor feature vectors that are closest to E_i (s is an experimental parameter, such as $s = 5$) and the maximum distance between E_i and s is represented by

$$d_s = \max_{l \in N_b(i, s)} \{d(E_i, A_l)\}. \quad (2.1)$$

The manifold measure is a ranking vector $r_Q = (r_i)$ is determined by solving the following objective function

$$EMR_Q(r) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i,j} w_{ij} \left\| \frac{r_i}{\sqrt{D_{ii}}} - \frac{r_j}{\sqrt{D_{jj}}} \right\|^2 + \mu \sum_i \|r_i - r_{0,i}\|^2 \right) \rightarrow \min, \quad (2.2)$$

with a validating phrase:

1. Q is selected in turn from E , $Q = E_k \in E$, $k = \overline{1, n}$;
2. the initial ranking vector is $r = r_0$ with

$$r_{0_k} = 1, r_{0_i} = 0, i = \overline{1, n}, i \neq k; \quad (2.3)$$

3. a kernel function is defined as

$$K(t) = \frac{3}{4} (1 - t^2), -1 \leq t \leq 1; \quad (2.4)$$

4. the spare weight matrix Z measuring the potential relationships between all data points and anchors is calculated by

$$Z = (z_{ci})_{1 \leq c \leq C, 1 \leq i \leq n}, z_{ci} = \frac{K\left(\frac{d(E_i, A_c)}{d_s}\right)}{\sum_{c' \in N_b(i; s)} K\left(\frac{d(E_i, A_{c'})}{d_s}\right)} \forall c \in N_b(i; s), z_{ci} = 0 \forall c \notin N_b(i; s); \quad (2.5)$$

5. the adjacency matrix W is defined as follows

$$W \stackrel{def}{=} Z^T Z, \text{ namely} \quad (2.6)$$

$$W = (w_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq n},$$

$$w_{ij} = \sum_{c \in N_b(i;s) \cap N_b(j;s)} z_{ci} * z_{cj}, 1 \leq i, j \leq n; \quad (2.7)$$

6. the diagonal matrix $D = (D_{ii})$, for all $i = \overline{1, n}$

$$D_{ii} \stackrel{def}{=} \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}; \quad (2.8)$$

and with a testing phrase:

1. Q is a given query image, $Q \notin E$;
2. E_{n+1} is assigned by Q ($E_{n+1} = Q$);
3. the initial ranking vector is $r = r_0$ with

$$r_{0_{n+1}} = 1, r_{0_i} = 0, i = \overline{1, n}; \quad (2.9)$$

4. the element $z_{k(n+1)}$ is added into the original matrix Z (Z is updated);

5. W is recalculated and updated new values as follows

$$W = Z^T Z = (w_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq n+1}, \quad (2.10)$$

$$w_{ij} = \sum_{c \in N_b(i;s) \cap N_b(j;s)} z_{ci} * z_{cj}, 1 \leq i, j \leq n+1; \quad (2.11)$$

6. for all $i = \overline{1, n+1}$

$$D_{ii} \stackrel{def}{=} \sum_{j=1}^{n+1} w_{ij}, \quad (2.12)$$

7. the obtained rankings on E are (r_i) , $i = \overline{1, n}$ (r_{n+1} is omitted)

Put $H = ZD^{-1/2}$, then $S = H^T H$ and

$$z_{n+1} \stackrel{def}{=} (z_{c,n+1})_{1 \leq c \leq C}, D_{n+1} \stackrel{def}{=} z_{n+1} v, h_{n+1} = z_{n+1} D_{n+1}^{-1/2}, H_{n+1} \stackrel{def}{=} H \oplus h_{n+1}.$$

$$r_Q = (r_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n} = \{(1 - \alpha)\alpha H^T B\} h_{n+1}. \quad (2.13)$$

According to ((2.13)), we have

$$r_Q = (r_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n} \approx \{(1 - \alpha)\alpha H^T B\} h_{n+1} = \alpha \left\{ (1 - \alpha) H^T (I_C - \alpha H H^T)^{-1} \right\}.$$

Let us transform the expression on the left-hand side into a sum

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= \alpha H^T (I_C - \alpha H H^T)^{-1} h_{n+1} = \alpha H^T \sum_{t=0}^{+\infty} (\alpha H H^T)^t h_{n+1} \\
 \Rightarrow r_{t+1,Q} &= \alpha H^T \sum_{i=0}^{t+1} (\alpha H H^T)^i h_{n+1} = \alpha H^T \left\{ I_C + \sum_{i=1}^{t+1} (\alpha H H^T)^i \right\} h_{n+1} \\
 &= \alpha H^T h_{n+1} + \alpha H^T \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{t+1} (\alpha H H^T)^i \right\} h_{n+1} \\
 &= \alpha H^T h_{n+1} + \alpha H^T \left\{ (\alpha H H^T) \sum_{i=0}^t (\alpha H H^T)^i \right\} h_{n+1} \\
 &= \alpha H^T h_{n+1} + \alpha H^T \left\{ (H(\alpha H^T)) \sum_{i=0}^t (\alpha H H^T)^i \right\} h_{n+1} \\
 &= \alpha H^T h_{n+1} + \alpha H^T H \left\{ (\alpha H^T) \sum_{i=0}^t (\alpha H H^T)^i \right\} h_{n+1} \\
 &= \alpha H^T h_{n+1} + \alpha (H^T H) \left\{ (\alpha H^T) \sum_{i=0}^t (\alpha H H^T)^i \right\} h_{n+1} \\
 &= \alpha H^T h_{n+1} + \alpha (H^T H) r_{t,Q} = \alpha S r_{t,Q} + \alpha H^T h_{n+1}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$r_Q = \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \overrightarrow{r_{t,Q}},$$

where

$$r_{t+1,Q} = \alpha H^T h_{n+1} + (\alpha H^T H) r_{t,Q} = \alpha S r_{t,Q} + \alpha H^T h_{n+1}.$$

Through Equation (2.2) and other equations calculating the related parameters Z, W, D , it can be noticed the ranking results obtained by the original EMR algorithm depend on selecting the quantity and the quality of the set of anchor points $\{A_c\}_{c=1}^C$. The ranking is accelerated by a new form of the adjacency matrix, which is designed in Equations (2.6), (2.7), (2.10), and (2.11). Based on the coefficients of W , data points are represented in a smaller new space of selected anchors. This helps EMR handle large databases with high dimensional vectors and gain fast computational speed of manifold ranking. The other discussions relating to the original EMR can be found in [37] and [29].

Manifold ranking in an image database with query images can be done by using multiple EMRs at the same time to enhance retrieval efficiency. In the study [30], an EMR is used to rank the low-level features of the images in

a dataset and another EMR on the embedded vectors that are extracted from this same dataset. Then, the rankings of each image obtained by two EMRs are combined into a mixed one. The final image retrieval result shows that the combination of rankings brings higher accuracy. However, this method is a semi-supervised approach, and training a large database to obtain the embedded vectors is costly in terms of storage resources and processing time. Therefore, it is relatively difficult to deploy a system that has a large image database.

The performance of CBIR needs to be further improved to meet the real problems of big data and the manifold property of the database. There are many related studies that proposed to upgrading the similarity measure inside EMR. Wu et al. [35] proposed a solution of combining only low-level features into a mixed feature, then normalized the feature vectors of images

to be more efficient in finding anchor points. In contrast, our research works on replacing K-means in EMR by FCM which is well-known as a soft clustering algorithm [21, 29, 30]. The reason for this solution is that the quality of manifold ranking depends on selecting of anchor points from a given database, so choosing a more rational clustering algorithm can gain the higher accuracy of image retrieval. We considered both FCM [5] and Spectral Clustering [6], then conducted the experiments on these algorithms. Finally, we compared the results and recognized that FCM is the best choice for clustering to determine the anchor points. In the next section, we focus on explaining the formulas of the original FCM and how to upgrade into *lvdc - FCM* so that it can handle the lvdc condition and is suitable for determining the relevant anchor points of an EMR Graph.

2.1.2. Fuzzy C-Means and lvdc - FCM

The advantage of the K-means algorithm is its simplicity and efficiency [38], however, it is a hard clustering algorithm and maintains a common limitation that each data point must belong to only one cluster. In contrast, FCM is known as a soft clustering algorithm that is

proven to be effective and widely used in pattern recognition [3]. FCM is proved more accurate than K-means thanks to allowing each data point to simultaneously belong to two or more clusters with different membership grades [4, 20]. This is the reason why FCM requires more processing time to calculate and update cluster centers. In our research direction, the original FCM is upgraded and replaced with K-means in EMR, so that the modification of FCM is applicable to a large database with a large number of clusters.

The objective function of FCM is represented by

$$J(A, \mu) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{c=1}^C \mu_{c,i}^p \|E_i - A_c\|^2 \rightarrow \min, \quad (2.14)$$

where $p > 1$ and $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean distance. The constraints for membership grades $\mu_{c,i}$ with $\forall i$ are given as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \mu_{c,i} \in [0, 1] \\ \sum_{c=1}^C \mu_{c,i} = 1 \\ \sum_i \mu_{c,i} > 0 \end{cases} \quad (2.15)$$

After solving (2.14) and (2.15), the parameters $\mu_{c,i}, A_c$ are obtained as follows:

$$\forall c = \overline{1, C}, \quad i = \overline{1, n},$$

$$\mu_{c,i} = \begin{cases} \max \left(\frac{1}{\sum_{\substack{1 \leq c' \leq C \\ i \in N_{best}(A_{c'})}} \left(\frac{\|E_i - A_c\|}{\|E_i - A_{c'}\|} \right)^{\frac{2}{m-1}}}, \mu_\epsilon \right) & \text{for } i \in N_{best}(A_c; n_b) \\ 0 & \text{for } i \notin N_{best}(A_c; n_b) \end{cases} \quad (2.16)$$

$$\forall c = \overline{1, C}, \quad A_c = \frac{\sum_{i'=1}^{n_b} \mu_{c, N_{best}(i')}^p E_{N_{best}(i')}}{\sum_{i'=1}^{n_b} \mu_{c, N_{best}(i')}^p}, \quad \forall c = \overline{1, C} \quad (2.17)$$

The involvement of the feature vectors E_i in Equation (2.17) while determining the anchor points from a database leads to some limitations. The first limitation is that the decision of selecting

cluster centers belongs to all of the vectors E_i while K-means only chooses the closest vectors to a given center A_c . Another restriction can be seen via Equation (2.16) that some membership grades $\mu_{c,i}$ may obtain very small values when n and C are large enough. This causes inefficiencies

in estimating cluster centers and a decrease in accuracy.

The algorithm *lvdc - FCM* is an improvement of the original FCM that its membership grades $\mu_{c,i}$ are adjusted as follows

$$\forall c = \overline{1, C}, i = \overline{1, n}, \mu_{c,i} = \left\{ \frac{1}{\sum_{i'=1}^n \left(\frac{\|E_i - A_c\|}{\|E_{i'} - A_c\|} \right)^{\frac{2}{p-1}}}, \mu_e \right\} \quad (2.18)$$

are normalized so that $\forall c = \overline{1, C}, \sum_{c=1}^C \mu_{c,i} = 1$. Finally, the clustering centers $\{A_c\}_{1 \leq c \leq C}$ is calculated by

$$\forall c = \overline{1, C}, A_c = \frac{\sum_{i'=1}^{n_b} \mu_{c, N_{best(c,i')}}^p E_{N_{best(c,i')}}}{\sum_{i'=1}^{n_b} \mu_{c, N_{best(c,i')}}^p}. \quad (2.19)$$

Equations (2.18) and (2.19) explain why *lvdc-FCM* can cluster a large database and handle the *lvdc* condition. There are two solutions attached to *lvdc-FCM* to overcome the above limitations of the original one. A threshold μ_ϵ is added into Equation (2.16) to filter the small values of membership grades that cause the inefficiency of FCM, so Equation (2.18) contains μ_ϵ that is a small enough positive constant. Instead of the whole E_i participating in the calculation, only a number n_b of the closest vectors $E_{i,c}$ to A_c are chosen to calculate the new anchor points in Equation (2.19) (in which $E_{N_{best(c,i)}}$ is the closest i^{th} vector). Thanks to the above improvements, the formulas of *lvdc - FCM* can handle the *lvdc* condition and is applicable to determine the relevant anchor points of a large database. The estimating of cluster centers is defined more accurately and efficiently because only the quality (closest) vectors are selected while all the vectors of E still involve and affect updating center points.

2.2. The proposed Manifold Ranking Algorithm based on low-level and CNN features

In this part, we propose an algorithm, called *cf-EMR*, for combining low-level and CNN features, where the images of a dataset are ranked with the improved EMR to obtain the outstanding advantages of both these feature types, thereby enhancing the retrieval quality. From our observation based on the manifolds of data and the distinct information provided by the different features, for each image, we concatenate the low-level feature vector which is normalized, and the extracted CNN feature vector to gain the beneficial characteristics of the image. Compared with the article [30] using multiple EMRs to rank different types of image features, in this paper, only the concatenation of the different feature vectors using one EMR has brought higher accuracy. Our experiments on several datasets show that using the combined features gives accurate results, which are vastly different from only combining the low-level features [20] or using a voting technique with multiple classifiers for the different aspects of the low-level features

2.2.1. *lvdc – EMR algorithm*

As mentioned in Section 2.2.1.1, the advantage of EMR is able to rank quickly and accurately the data points of an image database. The *lvdc – EMR* algorithm is an improvement of the original EMR by replacing K-means with *lvdc – FCM* (described in the previous section) that assigns the suitable anchor points for the EMR Graph. Thanks to this upgrade, *lvdc – EMR* not only handles *lvdc* conditions but also finds anchor points more efficiently.

For the improved *lvdc – EMR*, the new anchor points $\{A_c\}_{1 \leq c \leq C}$ of databases are recalculated by Formula (2.19) of *lvdc – FCM* in Section 2.1.2 2.2.1.2. Back to the calculation of EMR in Section 2.1.1 2.2.1.1, the maximum distances d_s between the vectors $\{E_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ and these anchor points are recalculated. The objective function is updated following Formula (2.2) along with the weight matrix Z , the adjacency matrix W , and the diagonal matrix D . Finally, for each Q the corresponding ranking vector r is calculated.

To increase the accuracy of image retrieval, in *lvdc – EMR* the low-level feature vectors of images are normalized by our $3\sigma - opt$ method [29]. This method was proven to be an effective normalization for non-Gaussian data so that each vector component of the image is in the range of $[-1, 1]$.

In terms of performance, *lvdc – FCM* in *lvdc – EMR* and K-means in EMR are equivalent. However, in terms of accuracy, *lvdc – EMR* is proven to increase significantly on the datasets, such as Corel30K and VGGFACE2-S. The accuracy of the image retrieval when using *lvdc – EMR* is better than EMR in both cases with or without relevance feedback. The experiments using *lvdc – EMR* on three low-level feature types (Color, Texture, Shape) with the feedback process is determined 98.6%. The effectiveness of *lvdc – EMR* without relevance feedback is increased up to 72.6% with a larger number C of vector clusters (see details in [21]).

Up to this point, *lvdc – EMR* can select

the quality anchors but is just applied to rank on the databases with low-level features. In this section, we focus on proposing a manifold ranking algorithm that accepts both low-level and CNN features. These feature types are concatenated into a combined one that represents the associated characteristics of images.

Algorithm cf-EMR is improved from *lvdc – EMR* so that it can receive an image dataset as an input and a pre-trained CNN model for extracting the corresponding CNN feature vectors. The cf-EMR algorithm uses a single improved EMR and returns the rankings of images by a given query image IQ. The algorithm contains two offline and one testing step. The offline steps are for calculating the combined feature vectors of an image dataset, finding the rational anchor points for the EMR graph, and computing the related matrices. The online step calculates the rankings of the images in the dataset by the query image $\{I_Q\}$. To present the cf-EMR algorithm, we assume that an original database contains the images which are represented respectively by the vectors $\{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots\}$. For each image I_i , the set of T different low-level features are extracted into the vectors $I_{t, i_{1 \leq t \leq T}}$ in Step 1.1. These vectors are normalized in Step 1.2 using the $3\sigma - opt$ method, which is applicable to the database with a non-Gaussian distribution, and spreads the values evenly over a range. In the next step, using a pre-trained CNN model Ω_1 , the corresponding CNN feature vector IE_i for each image is also obtained via transferring learning technique. Finally, Step 1.4 associates the normalized vector $\overline{I_{t,i}}$ and the extracted vector IE_i into a combined feature vector IC_i by concatenating the feature values.

2.2.2. *cf* – EMR algorithm

Algorithm 1: cf-EMR (Ω_1, T)- (Manifold ranking on the combined feature vectors of a dataset)

Ω_1 : pre-trained CNN model.

T : the number of low-level feature sets.

Input: image dataset $\{I_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$, query image I_Q .

C : the number of anchor points.

Output: $r = \{r_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$, $r_i \in [0, 1] \forall i = \overline{1, n}$ - the similarity value of IC_i ranked by I_Q .

Put: $I_{n+1} = I_Q$.

STEP 1 (offline):

1.1: Calculate low-level feature vectors

$\{I_{t,i}\}_{1 \leq t \leq T, 1 \leq i \leq n}$ of $\{I_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$.

1.2: Normalize the low-level feature vectors using the 3σ – *opt* method and obtain

$\{\overline{I_{t,i}}\}_{1 \leq t \leq T, 1 \leq i \leq n}$.

1.3: For each image I_i , calculate CNN feature vectors $\{IE_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ using model Ω_1 .

1.4: Concatenate low feature vectors with CNN feature vectors

$$\begin{aligned} & \{\overline{I_{t,i}}\}_{1 \leq t \leq T, 1 \leq i \leq n} \oplus \{IE_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} \\ & = \{IC_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} \text{ for each image } I_i. \end{aligned}$$

STEP 2 (offline): Determine C anchors and the weights w_{ij} of the EMR graph by applying a *lvdc* – *FCM*.

2.1 Initialize the centers of *lvdc* – *FCM* by selecting C different random vectors from $\{IC_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$

2.2 Calculate the membership matrix $\{\mu_{c,i}\}_{1 \leq c \leq C, 1 \leq i \leq n}$ according to Formula (2.18) (Perform on GPU platform)

2.3 Normalize and obtain the weight matrix as follows (Perform on GPU platform):

$$\mu_{c,i} = \frac{\mu_{c,i}}{\sum_{c'=1}^C \mu_{c',i}}, c = \overline{1, C}, i = \overline{1, n}$$

2.4 Recalculate the centers of the cluster $\{A_c\}_{1 \leq c \leq C}$ according to Formula (2.19) (Perform on GPU platform).

2.5 Calculate $J_l(A, \mu)$ according to Formula (2.14).

2.6 Get out the loop if

$|J_l(A, \mu) - J_{l-1}(A, \mu)|$ is less than a threshold or l is bigger than the number of loops for training the objective function.

2.7 Calculate Z , W and D that support to determine the vector ranking r_I of each image I in E (see details in [37]).

STEP 3 (testing for I_Q):

3.1 Initialize

$$r_Q = \{r_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n+1}, r_i = 0 \forall i = \overline{1, n}, r_{n+1} = 1.0$$

3.2 Calculate ranking values

$r_Q = (r_{Q,i})_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ based on the combined feature vectors $\{IC_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n+1}$ by using an EMR.

3.3 Return r_Q

STEP 2 of cf-EMR is also conducted offline where the data points of the dataset are built into an EMR graph in order to calculate the coordinates of all anchors C . The steps 2.1 - 2.7 compute in turn the values following the formulas that are represented in Section 2.1 and Section 2.2. The weight w_{ij} representing the adjacency relationship of two images I_i and I_j is also determined via the matrix W . All coefficients

determined in STEP 1 and STEP 2 are saved and used for STEP 3.

Finally, the testing step calculates on the combined features IC and returns the ranking values r_Q of the image dataset following I_Q by using an EMR.

3. CBIR system with applied $cf - EMR$

3.1. CBIR system structure

In this section, we focus on depicting the proposed CBIR system that applies the algorithm $cf-EMR$. The process of working and ranking on the combination of different feature vectors is shown in Figure 1. The input images of the CBIR system are represented by both low-level features and CNN features. The offline and testing phases of $cf-EMR$ are integrated with this figure, the algorithm $lvdc - FCM$ updates the quality anchors of the database, and the EMR Graph based on these anchor points is established. Finally, the retrieval result is a set of images that are ranked at the top for the user following the image query.

For low-level features, we select three basic types, including color, texture, and shape [12, 19, 27] for representing images. Namely, five sets of low-level features (Color Moments, LBP, Gabor Wavelets Texture, Edge, and GIST) are extracted from datasets. All of these features are normalized using the $3\sigma - opt$ method [29] so that each vector element of each image falls within the range $[-1, 1]$. These low-level features contain the characteristics of an image that are represented in a high-dimensional vector, namely $d_{lf} = 809$ (see Table 1), with less semantics compared to the CNN feature but without losing image details.

There are many deep neural networks that carry information about the complexity of images that is meaningful to people [23], such as VGG16, ResNet-v2-152, EfficientNet, etc. EfficientNets is a family of models that achieve much better accuracy and efficiency than other networks [28].

In particular, the EfficientNet-B7 achieves state-of-the-art 84.3% top-1 accuracy on the ImageNet dataset, while being 8.4 times smaller and 6.1 times faster on inference than the best existing ConvNet. Therefore, in this paper, we choose the pre-trained model of the EfficientNet-B7 network for extracting CNN features. Using transfer learning techniques on large image datasets we obtain high-level characteristics of images.

As mentioned above, we use EfficientNet-B7 as a feature extractor for the CBIR system. This model was trained on ImageNet with 14 million images labeled on 21K groups. We trim the last layers of this network to get a network model for extracting feature vectors. The number of the network layers is 806 which corresponds to 7 blocks and 1 subblock of input layer. After an image dataset passes through this EfficientNet network, the feature vector set is obtained with dimensions of 1280 values (see Table 1).

Table 1: Properties of features.

Description	Feature	Size of feature vector
GCM	Color	81
LBP	Texture	59
GWT	Texture	120
EDH	Shape	37
GIST	Shape	512
From EfficientNet-B7	CNN	1280

In summary, all extracted features of a image (including five sets of low-level features and CNN feature) are combined into a unique feature vector with a total size of 2089 ($809 + 1280$) values (see details in Table 1). Euclidean distance is used to calculate the distances between images based on their the combined feature vectors and also to compare the feature similarity measure of the query image with the rest of the database.

3.2. Datasets

We select three image datasets Logo2K+ [14], VGGFACE2-S [24], and Corel30K [11],

which are sorted in ascending order of complexity, for conducting the experiments in this article. The first dataset Logo2K+ contains 22725 logo images of 441 different brands that are placed in 441 groups, each of which includes 75 images of each brand. Figure 2 shows some image samples in the Logo2K+ dataset. The second dataset is VGGFACE2-S which is a subset of the image dataset VGGFACE2 for face recognition. This dataset consists of 61750 images that are divided into 494 groups, each of which includes 125 images of each person. Figure 3 shows some of the image samples in VGGFACE2-S, which are different in size, resolution, and color.

The last dataset Corel30K has 30887 complex visualized images that are divided into 306 items by themes and semantic sense, and are illustrated in Figure 4.

For conducting the experiments in this article, we set the parameter $\mu_\varepsilon = 10^{-6}$ and the different value of n_b in the *ldvc - FCM* algorithm for each dataset, namely, $n_b = 150$ for Logo2K+, $n_b = 500$ for VGGFACE2-S and $n_b = 350$ for Corel30K. To objectively evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm cf-EMR compared with the original EMR algorithm, we use a mean average precision (called mAP) proposed by NISTTREC video (TRECVID) [36]. mAP is defined as the average of the accuracy values that are obtained after each search for relevant images (see more in [21]).

The query image set $\{Q\}$ is randomly selected with the amount of 10% according to each topic of the test datasets Logo-2K+, VGGFACE2-S, and Corel30K. Depending on the number of images, image classes and the number of images in each class, the parameter C (the number of anchor points) will be selected while performing the experiments on these datasets. The value of C varies from 1000 to 10000 based on the experiments and are chosen so that the most accurate retrieval result is received for each image dataset. Accelerating Anchor Points selection when using *ldvc - FCM*, at the step of recalculating each cluster center A_c (see equations 15 and 16), we need to determine

n_b data vector points closest to A_c . To achieve this, we have utilized Approximation Nearest Neighbor (ANN) search technique, specifically by using the FAISS library [39]. Furthermore, when experimenting with features extraction on Logo2K+, VGGFACE2S, and Corel30K datasets using the EfficientNet-B7 model, we can utilize fine-tuning techniques to improve the accuracy of *cf - EMR* ranking results.

4. Experimental results

To evaluate the result of this paper from different perspectives, we conduct the following three experiments with cf-EMR to obtain the image retrieval accuracy, analyzing retrieval results and comparing them to other authors.

4.1. Evaluation of the *ldvc - FCM* algorithm

In this experimental section, to evaluate the clustering quality of the *ldvc - FCM* algorithm with the original FCM algorithm, we use indexes such as the Xie-Beni index [25] and IFVIndex (Index of Fuzzy Validity) [10, 31]. Xie-Beni validity indices have been often used for evaluating the quality of Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) cluster partitions because they can validate fuzzy partitions considering the geometrical features of clusters, which suit human feelings in most cases. The range of values for Xie Beni is from 0 to infinity, with lower values representing a better degree of clustering. Usually, Xie-Beni is used to compare the clustering between different algorithms or between different clustering methods for the same data set and is mainly used for the family of fuzzy clustering. The lower the index, the better the clustering. The index of Fuzzy Validity (IFVIndex) is a measure used to evaluate the quality of fuzzy clustering in the ability to divide groups and the fuzziness of clustering. The IFVIndex provides an evaluative metric of the separation and concentration of clustering groups, based on the fuzziness and

FIG. 1: (Color online) Flow-chart of CBIR with combined feature vectors.

FIG. 2: (Color online) Logo-2K+ images.

concentration values of the data points in each group. The value of the IFVIndex measure in the experiment is directly proportional to the performance of the implemented algorithm.

Using the t-SNE and PCA data

dimensionality reduction methods, visualize the LF809 dimensional low-level feature data of the Corel30K set as in Figure 5.

FIG. 3: (Color online) VGGFACE2-S images.

FIG. 4: (Color online) Corel30K images.

4.2. Accuracy with different feature types

We compare the accuracy that is obtained after performing the experiments on three datasets with three cases of using feature types: lower-level features, CNN features, and combined features, shown in Table 2. The parameter C is chosen suitably so that the accuracy of the retrieval is the maximum value for each case. The experimental results show that the image retrieval accuracy increases significantly, especially with the VGGFACE2-S dataset reaching 93.5% in the case of using the combined feature, which is 10,1% higher than in the case of using only the CNN feature. In addition, on the larger dataset Corel30K which has high visual representation and complex semantics, the accuracy with the combined feature also increases by more than 10% compared to the CNN feature and more than 20% compared to the low-level features. The results of the image retrieval on three datasets Logo-2K+, VGGFACE2-S, and Corel30K without the RF process show the ranking effectiveness of $cf - EMR$.

Table 2: Xie-Beni index and IFVIndex on dataset LF809 of data set Corel30K

Algorithm	Xie-Beni index	IFVIndex
FCM	0.00412	118.2531745545215
lvdc - FCM	0.00249	119.1000254356127

4.3. Accuracy on EMRs

To further clarify the effectiveness of the $cf - EMR$ algorithm as well as the proposal for using the combined feature of images in this article, we conduct the experiments to compare the manifold ranking accuracy of using the original EMR with using $cf - EMR$, shown in Table 3. From the data in the table, it can be seen that a large gap in accuracy is obtained across all datasets. These results also demonstrate the feasibility of

our research direction that focuses on improving EMRs to bring better CBIR systems.

4.4. Accuracy with relevance feedback

RF is considered a method to reduce the gap between low-level visual features and high-level semantic concepts by allowing the interaction between the user and the image retrieval system to obtain feedback samples [11, 17]. In this section, to compare we only choose three low-level feature sets, namely Color and Texture (LBP and GWT), which are the same as the inputs set up for the experiments in [11]. The CNN feature extracted from EfficientNet-B7 model is still used as a high-level feature. In this section, we conduct four minor experiments to compare the results that are obtained by using or not using RF.

The first line in Table 5 is the result conducted by applying lvdc-EMR on three sets of low-level features. The accuracy of image retrieval increases from 3% to 7% in the second minor experiment that is set up as the first one but uses RF over 5 loops. The highest score is VGGFACE2-S's, reaching 73%. The result 69.9% on Corel30K (the most complex dataset used in this paper) is even higher than the SEMAL system mentioned in [11] which reaches less than 60%.

Using our proposed algorithm $cf - EMR$ in this paper, the CBIR system even shows more efficiency in the third minor experiment (see the third line of Table 5). The inputs are three sets of low-level features and CNN feature (which are combined) while the outputs are the rankings of the images with more than 80% accuracy without using RF. This result is achieved thanks to $cf - EMR$ obtaining the advantages of all feature types and containing itself an efficient ranking method. Therefore, $cf - EMR$ increases the retrieval accuracy by more than 20% compared to lvdc-EMR which accepts only low-level features.

The final line of Table 5 represents the experimental results of the fourth minor experiment that is proceeded the same way as

Table 3: Retrieval accuracy with *cf-EMR* on different feature types.

	Logo-2K+	VGGFACE2-S	Corel30K
Low-level features	69.6%	73.1%	61.6%
	(C=5500)	(C=6000)	(C=6000)
CNN feature	74.9%	83.4%	71.8%
	(C=7000)	(C=7000)	(C=5000)
Combined feature	89.6%	93.5%	82.2%
	(C=5500)	(C=7000)	(C=5000)

Table 4: The original EMR and *cf-EMR* on combined feature.

	Logo-2K+	VGGFACE2-S	Corel30K
Original EMR	63.2%	68.8%	69.7%
	(C=6000)	(C=5500)	(C=5000)
<i>cf-EMR</i>	89.6%	93.5%	82.2%
	(C=5500)	(C=7000)	(C=5000)

the third one but repeated on 5 loops of RF. These values are higher those of the second and third minor experiments. Especially, with a complex dataset as Corel30K, our proposed method achieves 85.9% which increases 5.4% compared to the case of not using RF. The highest accuracy is 89.8% on VGGFACE2-S.

All experimental results shown in Table 5 prove that *cf-EMR* is an effective algorithm for ranking images in both cases of using or not using RF.

5. Conclusions

The paper presents the *cf-EMR* algorithm that combines low-level features and CNN feature which are extracted from the images in a dataset, then ranks these images under a condition of large numbers of image vectors, vector dimensions and clusters. The proposed direction of the paper contributes to overcoming the limitations of basic similarity measures as well as taking the advantages of different feature types.

The experimental results with *cf-EMR* on several datasets, which contain the complex visual concepts, obtain the high retrieval accuracy. The

algorithm has proven the retrieval effectiveness and applicability in solving real-world problems relating to CBIR.

In future, we continue to improve the proposed algorithm *cf-EMR* in terms of processing speed and image retrieval performance on very large image datasets which contain more complex details. We also consider different dimensionality reduction techniques that are able to be applied for high dimensional image vectors but do not affect retrieval results. To improve the potency of *cf-EMR* we will study on integrating several machine learning methods to build a model to predict similarity measures between two images based on their low-level features and CNN feature. This solution can enhance the processing speed by filtering and ranking only part of the dataset thereby improving retrieval efficiency. The combination of multiple EMRs is also a promising research direction that we will work towards.

Acknowledgment

This research is funded by VNU – University of Education under Reascher Project number QS.22.09.

Table 5: lvdc-EMR and cf-EMR on different feature types.

	Logo-2K+	VGGFACE2-S	Corel30K
Color, Texture(LBP, GWT)	61.4%	68.7%	66.9%
with lvdc-EMR	(C=5500)	(C=6000)	(C=6000)
Color, Texture(LBP, GWT)	68.8%	73.7%	69.9%
with lvdc-EMR and RF (5 loops)	(C=5500)	(C=6000)	(C=6000)
Color, Texture(LBP, GWT), CNN	82.5%	88.2%	80.5%
with cf-EMR	(C=5500)	(C=7000)	(C=5000)
Color, Texture(LBP, GWT), CNN	83.8%	89.8%	85.9%
with cf-EMR and RF (5 loops)	(C=5500)	(C=7000)	(C=5000)

FIG. 5: (Color online) Visualization of 809D feature vector data with t-SNE (left) and 3-D PCA (right) of Corel30K.

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